

Post-Task Survey

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. Rounded to the closest year, for how many years have you been programming? *

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10+

3. Rounded to the closest year, for how many years have you been programming **with Java**? *

Mark only one oval.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10+

4. Do you have experience in professional software development? *

Check all that apply.

- Yes, as full-time employment
- Yes, as an internship or co-op
- Yes, I contribute to open-source software
- Yes, self-employed
- No

Experience with Code Review

5. Do you have experience with code refactoring in a professional environment? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

6. Do you have experience with code reviews in a professional environment? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

7. Do you have professional experience providing reviews on others' code through GitHub? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

8. Do you have professional experience receiving feedback from others on your code through GitHub? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

On Comparing Code

9. What was difficult about performing the code review in this study? *

10. What was easy about performing the code review in this study? *

11. What would have helped you perform the code review in this study more effectively? *

Demography

12. What type of student are you? *

Mark only one oval.

Part-time

Full-time

Other: _____

13. What is your major? *

14. What is/are your minor(s), if any? *

15. What is your gender identity? *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to disclose

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